

FEATURES OF THE ORGANIZATION OF THE ACCOUNTING OF FINANCIAL RESULTS FOR EXTRA-BUDGETARY FUNDS IN INSTITUTIONS OF THE PEOPLE'S EDUCATION SYSTEM.

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Abstract: *This article provides the current state of the organization of accounting of financial results of institutions of the people's education system on extra-budgetary funds, the procedure for maintaining and ways to improve accounting. Also, recommendations have been formed on the effective and high-quality formation of accounting of public educational institutions and improving the accounting of financial results.*

Key words: *budget organization, income, funds, financing, financial result, financial statements, expense.*

It is necessary to improve the current state of the organization of accounting of financial results of institutions of the public education system on extra-budgetary funds, the procedure for maintaining and accounting, as well as to effectively and qualitatively form accounting of public educational institutions, and to improve the accounting of financial results. Measures related to increasing the share of extra-budgetary funds in financing the activities of institutions of the people's education system are being implemented in our country in accordance with the requirements of the market economy, as well as in order to reduce the budget burden and establish training of personnel based on the requirements of the market economy. The people's education system is presented by drawing up financial reports on the behavior of extra-budgetary funds in order to ensure the execution of estimates of institutions, the financial condition of institutions, the targeted use of budgetary and extra-budgetary funds, transparency of information on budget execution.

Based on the nature of the activities of the founders of the people's education system, the need arises to determine the state of financing from the budget and the possibility of the formation of extra-budgetary funds, to carry out an analysis of financial statements on the behavior of extra-budgetary funds of institutions in order to achieve targeted spending of funds. This necessitates people's educational institutions to conduct research on the analysis of reports on the movement of extra-budgetary funds.

The main purpose of determining financial results in budgetary organizations is to determine the value of the organization's net assets by comparing the income

received by the organization for the current period and the expenses incurred. In the institutions of the people's education system, we will consider the financial result in order to determine the difference between the income and expenses of the funds of the development fund, that is, by determining the financial result, whether the funds are spent purposefully and efficiently, or vice versa. The initial stage in determining the financial result is an assessment of the financial year and the activities of the organization by determining the difference between income and expenses between one financial year. The sequence, periodicity of the procedure for determining the financial result is regulated by the Instruction No. 2169 (2010).

By analyzing the data in financial statements, attention is paid to determining the current financial condition of the budget organization and determining the possibility of financing from the budget and the formation of extra-budgetary funds based on the result of the organization's activities, as well as its targeted spending. Generalization of financial statements on the movement of extra-budgetary funds of institutions of the people's education system by analyzing the indicators associated with them, it is possible to form data on the role and importance of extra-budgetary funds in budgetary organizations.

As a result of the analysis of the data in the presented financial statements, financial decisions are made by determining and assessing the current financial condition of the budget organization, forming forecast data, and ways are sought to determine the state of financing from the budget and the possibility of forming extra-budgetary funds based on the result of the organization's activities, as well.

The following proposals will be made on the current state of the organization of accounting of financial results of institutions of the people's education system for extra-budgetary funds, the procedure for maintaining and the effective and high-quality formation of accounting, improving the accounting of financial results:

- determination of the results of activities on commodity business services in the development fund, and the correct reflection in the structure of the development fund's revenue activities;

- it is necessary to have a separate methodological support aimed at recognizing income and expenses on extra-budgetary funds or determining financial results i.e., a clear definition of criteria for recognizing income and expenses based on the standards determines the occurrence of relations associated with them, rules and methods for maintaining the account;

- it is necessary to ensure timely and targeted spending of the remaining funds paid to the amount of benefits for used taxes and other mandatory payments in order to strengthen the material base of the organization;

- it is necessary to establish the procedure for taking into account issues related to income that are delayed by the deadline in the case associated with the lease.

In conclusion, it can be noted that in budgetary organizations it is necessary to make changes to the current state and procedure for maintaining the accounting of financial results on extra-budgetary funds, to effectively and qualitatively form accounting, and to improve the accounting of financial results.

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